

Master in Sound and Music Computing
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Computational Segmentation of Sheet Music Books for Search and Retrieval

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Abstract

Music books frequently includes numerous compositions or pieces in a singular volume. The manual segmentation of these compositions can be time intensive. The difficulty escalates further when handling scanned or digitized PDFs, particularly in the absence of explicit metadata or a table of contents. Recent progress in computational methods presents encouraging strategies for automatically dividing these musical volumes. IMSLP is full of books, but we cannot analyse them with MIR techniques because many tasks, specifically difficulty or structure analysis, require the books to be divided into pieces.

In this thesis the idea is to use DTW (Dynamic Time Warping) and OMR (Optical Music Recognition) to create a dataset with sheet music divided into pieces. The dataset will be created automatically but requires human in the loop to ensure that the ground truth is reliable and confident. We expect to create an interface to generate this dataset, using PDFs at the entrance and obtaining the different pieces of the sheet music. This GUI will suggest potential segmentation points allowing the user to make the final decision.

Keywords: bootleg score; segmentation; DTW ; OMR

Chapter 1

Introduction

The field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) has been in constant evolution since the late 1990s, when the availability of digital music became more common and computational methods for analyzing and organizing music data began to improve.

In addition, the adoption of digital music platforms, online streaming services, and the growing interest in music recommendation systems contributed to the visibility and importance of MIR. Furthermore, academic conferences dedicated to this topic, such as the International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR) [1] conference, have played a crucial role in incrementing research and collaboration within the field.

One of the most important factors when working with Machine Learning [2] is the quality of the data used to train the different models, which directly influences on their performance when processing new samples. For example, when it comes to analyzing the difficulty or structure of music pieces, having an appropriate dataset for this task can be challenging, due to the lack of correctly labeled data available on the internet.

1.1 Motivation

In my case, music has been a part of my life since I was a child. When I started to learn music, one thing that amazed me was the possibilities that a sheet music provides to an artist, which are practically infinite. A musical score is rarely played mechanically [3], and a musical piece represented in one way could be played varying the tempo, dynamics, and articulation depending on the musicians and how they feel at the moment of the performance.

In the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) [4], music representation takes various forms, with symbolic music being utilized to extract information from sheet music representations. This approach contrasts with traditional music composition, where composers typically rely on their intuition, musical training, and personal expression to create music. Symbolic music often explores concepts related to mathematics, computer science, and other abstract principles, leading to highly complex and innovative musical compositions.

Some of the most common representations include Piano-Roll [5], MIDI [6], and MusicXML [7]. Additionally, with the evolution of computational power and machine learning techniques, Optical Music Recognition (OMR) has become increasingly important. Quoting from the article published by J. Calvo-Zaragoza, JH Jr and A. Pacha [8], "While musicians can read and interpret very complex music scores, there is still no computer system that is capable of doing so." Despite this last statement, computers are capable of represent the information available in a digital image, as it can be interpreted as a representation of rows and columns of pixels, where each pixel also encodes information related to color. This is very important considering that sheet music is usually represented as a black and white image with different pixels that machines can analyse, regardless the "deeper" meaning of the musical piece.

On the other hand, when we analyze the monthly users of IMSLP (International Music Score Library Project), we can see that the number of users is 3.5 million per month. This website has the largest music library in the world, but it is not possible

to perform MIR tasks that require the books to be divided into pieces (specifically difficulty or structure analysis) because we do not know the location of the individual compositions within the book. It is important to understand that the term piece is subjective, but we refer to it as a musical unit that has enough content to be analyzed separately, movements in most of the cases.

For example, sonatas can be divided into three or four parts. If someone wants to perform a technical analysis of a piece or study the difficulties that it presents for a pianist, the first movement will have a different difficulty from the second movement of the score. In addition, the majority of data available in this project corresponds to books that contains numerous musical pieces by the same composer, which can be completely different or independent from each other.

This is due to the fact that many classical music works are no longer under copyright, so it is very common to group multiple music scores into a single book. To summarize, in this project we want to segment the books in different parts with clear metadata, which will be very useful to perform future tasks such as composer, difficulty or style classification

In addition, sometimes the access to download the books can be difficult, and there are other problems that we may encounter. Segmenting these compositions manually can be tedious and time consuming. This process becomes even more challenging when dealing with scanned or digitized PDF's, especially when there's no clear metadata or table of contents. Recent progress in computational methods presents encouraging strategies for automatically dividing these musical volumes.

1.2 Piano Library

When we tried to find information on the internet to search for and retrieve sheet music, we realised that this data was very limited or practically non-existent. After a search for possible sources of information, we found a website called *Piano Library*.

This website contains a database of more than 5000 pieces of music, for which relevant information is available such as the composer, the difficulty of the piece

and a link to IMSLP where you can access the book or music score containing the specific piece of music. An example of the information available on the website is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Piano Library Website Example.

Understanding this is very important, as it will form the basis of our work. As we can see in **Figure 1**, what we find in *Piano Library* is a short fragment (usually a staff) in PNG format. As mentioned above, apart from the information about the piece, there is also a link to IMSLP where the book containing the complete piece is available.

This is where we come to the key to our project and why we want to do it in a specific way. On the one hand, we have small fragments (images in PNG format) corresponding to different pieces, of which we know the composer, the difficulty... On the other hand, we have access to complete books with different sheet music inside. If what we are interested in is to have books divided into pieces, why not use the fragments available in *Piano Library* to find their position in the complete book and thus get the segmented books with its corresponding metadata?

To do this, we will use the small fragments available in *Piano Library*, find their position within a book and annotate the necessary data to segment all the documents efficiently. In our case, we will use OMR to perform our task. Although the use of OMR may not be necessary in future tasks (or maybe it is necessary, we don't know at the moment), in our case and with the information we have, it is very useful and simple to perform.

In this thesis, we will work with a mid-level representation called *Bootleg Score* [9], that encodes the rules of Western musical notation using information from the digital image such as staff lines, bar lines and filled noteheads. The details of how this representation works will be included in the following sections of this document.

In conclusion, the relevance of this work is to create a dataset with sheet music divided into pieces and its corresponding metadata [10], being pioneers in researching how to identify where a piece starts in music books. This task is important because, without that information, a machine cannot learn to differentiate between individual compositions. The dataset will be created automatically but requires human in the loop to ensure that the ground truth is reliable and confident.

1.3 Objectives

The estimated work plan and objectives for this thesis are:

- Obtain the initial PDF books and fragments from the *Piano Library* website.
- Test if the Bootleg generation works well.
- Use of DWT and OMR to see if the detection of the fragments can be implemented.
- Developing of a GUI tool that suggests potential segmentation points, allowing the user to make the final decision.
- Propose a simple ML baseline for future work with the dataset.

1.4 Structure of the thesis

This thesis is structured into different sections, each one of them having a specific purpose in the presentation and exploration of the project:

Following the introduction, the State of the Art section provides information about existing literature and research relevant to the topic, evaluating previous works,

highlighting key concepts and methodologies. In our case, this section will focus on explaining how the Bootleg Score really works, which is not explained anywhere else and can be very useful for new researchers.

The Methodology section describes the methods used for data collection, GUI design, and analysis. In our specific case, this section would include the different steps followed in order to obtain the necessary PDF music books for creating the dataset, as well as the tools used to perform the segmentation.

In the Results section, the statistics and analysis of the dataset are presented. The Discussion section examines the implications of our work, considers their limitations, and explores potential directions for future research. The conclusions are also included in this section.

Finally, a Bibliography section is included with all the sources cited throughout the document.

Chapter 2

State of the art

Before introducing the methodology and results of this project, it is important to understand the different concepts that will be mentioned throughout the document. As we will see in a few moments, we use OMR for the task we want to do. The problem is that nowadays, the OMR field has made some progress, but there are many cases in which the results are not good enough or simply do not work. However, it is not possible to perform a lot of tasks in real life with existing libraries, because the majority of sheet music is located in books.

If we have two different websites where we can find useful information to make a dataset with correctly segmented books, from which we have useful metadata for each case, why not take advantage of that information and create a dataset that can be used in different tasks? Likewise, there are many ways to perform segmentation, but if we have methods that use OMR to achieve our objective efficiently, it is also logical to take advantage of the benefits that these new tools provide us with. In addition, it is very motivating to know that the work we do by grouping all the data can be used by other researchers in future work.

As mentioned in previous sections, we chose to work with a low-resource representation called Bootleg Score, that has already been used for MIDI passage retrieval [9] or composer style classification [11]. Using Bootleg Score is not necessary for future tasks, or it might not be necessary, that is a question that we cannot answer

at this moment. But as we will see, for the task we are doing of creating a dataset semi-automatically using the information of 2 different websites, it is a good and useful option.

Finally, Python functions that perform specific tasks in generating the Bootleg Score will be explained in the following sections. All the code used in this project is open source to facilitate reproducibility (How To Use Bootleg Score). In case of any questions, do not hesitate to contact the author of this document.

2.1 OMR

Optical Music Recognition (OMR) has been one of the most important fields within the music computing community during the past few years, with many algorithms and metrics being released that allow engineers to work with musical information. Furthermore, the industry has been evolving exponentially with the use of digital platforms for listening to music, as well as the increasing need for adequate data to obtain good results when using machine learning techniques.

According to J. Calvo-Zaragoza et al [8], Optical Music Recognition is a field of research that investigates how to computationally read music notation in documents. Music can be understood as a framework of notes arranged over time, being a universally recognized visual language used for transcription. A note, a fundamental element of music, is characterized by four attributes: pitch, duration, volume, and timbre. Moreover, each note has an onset (a point in time that indicates when it begins) which in music isn't measured by standard time units but rather by relative beats. Intervals of silence within musical pieces, denoted by rests, are marked by their onset and duration. Both notes and rests can be organized into graphical structures, like groups of eighth notes joined by a beam, and logical structures such as phrases or voices. This organization is fundamental for the comprehension and interpretation of compositions.

Some of the more important applications when talking about OMR can be the following:

Replayability: Extracting the coded musical information regarding pitch, tempo, onset, and length. Within this framework, OMR enables the integration of music notation documents as an input for a computer.

Structured Encoding : Retrieving the music and its notation. This method focuses on providing a musical score that needs to be accurately re-encoded, assuming people will directly interpret the OMR output.

As mentioned before, the OMR field has made some progress, but there are many cases where the results are not good enough or simply do not work. That is why we decided to work with Bootleg Score, a mid-level music representation that facilitates music sheet processing without requiring significant computational power or extensive libraries and dependencies. Thanks to the advantages provided by Bootleg Score, carrying out our task of creating a dataset using the Piano Library fragments to find their location in a book can be very useful.

2.2 Bootleg Score

Bootleg Score representation was created by TJ Tsai [9] and his lab from Harvey Mudd College, which seeks to represent the position of filled notes on a staff using zeros and ones, explicitly encoding the rules of Western Music Notation for piano sheet music. The following sections will explain this representation based on the code created by TJ Tsai and his lab, which will be very useful for obtaining deeper insights.

This symbolic representation encodes the information of the filled noteheads of the sheet music, which includes quarter notes, eighth notes, and sixteenth notes [12]. Thus, there is some information that will not be included. This problem was encountered during the process of our research, where some musical scores only contain whole or half notes, making Bootleg Score useless when trying to compare the music book with the individual composition fragment.

When initializing a PDF music book, the Bootleg Score will be generated page by page, and after obtaining the bootleg representations of all the pages, they are

concatenated into a full matrix with dimensions of $62 \times N$, where 62 represents the possible staff positions and N represents the number of simultaneous events. After choosing an specific file, the *convert* function from the ImageMagick [13] package will convert each of the pages in an individual *png* file. During this process, each image will be resized to have a width of 2550 pixels. The image will be resized again using the function *calcResizedDimensions()* before performing the feature extraction tasks. This details about the resizing of the images will be important when retrieving the information to represent the detected noteheads and the detected fragment in the original PDF.

To obtain the Bootleg Score representation, it is necessary to extract three different types of information from each page: Staff lines, filled noteheads and bar lines (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Bootleg Score generation overview.

2.2.1 Notehead Detection

In the case of notehead detection, a morphological circle filter is calculated to detect filled noteheads, and then blob detection is done using the *SimpleBlobDetector* module from OpenCV [14]. It returns the keypoints found, which are used to obtain the note template (**Figure 3**).

The function *adaptiveNoteheadDetect()* performs the adaptive detection of noteheads from our image. The function uses Otsu's binarization [15] to convert the

Figure 3: Steps to obtain the noteheads of the sheet music.

input image into a binarized image. Then, it labels the connected regions in the binarized image and studies each region to determine if it represents an individual notehead or a block of chords. The detected noteheads are stored in a list called *notes*, and the function returns this list along with the binarized image.

Finally, with the notes list data (*nhlocs*), we can obtain the require information of all the noteheads detected. Another function takes a list of bounding boxes representing noteheads, calculates the central coordinates of each one of them, and provides an average estimation of the width and length of the noteheads in that list. These estimations can be useful for adjusting or normalizing the dimensions of noteheads in a specific context.

To visualize the detected noteheads in the original image, we also return the value of the scale factor used in the *calcResizedDimensions()* function, which was used to calculate all the previous information. With both the noteheads' locations and the scale factor, it is possible to use *cv2.circle* to visualize the results and identify any potential mistakes. For example, a common error is the detection of noteheads in the title of the sheet music. This is understandable, considering that depending on the font used in the title and its width, the morphological filter may detect a coincidence in that area. Another common mistake is detecting a notehead in the tails of the treble and bass clefs, which are typically represented with a circular form.

2.2.2 Staff Line Detection

Looking to the code, the first thing that is done is the isolation of the estimated staff lines using the function *isolateStaffLines()*. It uses morphological operations to isolate the staff lines in an image. First, the horizontal lines are identified and then the note bars are removed to obtain only the staff lines.

Secondly, *computeStaveFeatureMap()* returns the resulting feature map, staff lengths, and column width. This feature map is used to analyze patterns in the sheet music image, specifically to detect musical staves.

Once we have the *nhlocs* values and the feature map obtained in *computeStaveFeatureMap()*, it is possible to obtain all the information about the stave lines. With the *getEstStaffLineLocs()* function, we have a list of predictions where each prediction is a tuple containing the initial and final position of a staff line, the associated column and row, and the corresponding index in the *featmap*.

Then, *estimateStaffMidpoints()* groups the midpoint of the estimated staff lines and dynamically adjusts the number of clusters according to a threshold criteria.

```
staveMidpts = ([20.7142, 331.8684, 467.6111, 686.3090,
               842.5256, 1066.2065, 1189.1956, 1399.7954, 1541.39])
```

The next step consists of assigning the noteheads to the staff that corresponds to them. It also calculates the difference between the noteheads location and the center of the assigned staff line.

```
staveIdxs = ([0,0,0,0,0,0,0,1,1,1,1,1,1...])
```

In the code above, each index corresponds to a notehead, and the value corresponds to a specific staff. So, in that case, the first 8 notes will correspond to the first staff, while the following will be assigned to the second staff. Finally, notehead values on the sheet music are estimated based on the previous staff line predictions.

2.2.3 Bar Line Detection

In the Bar Line detection part, bounding boxes are predicted around the bar lines in the image. Bar lines are necessary to properly group the staff lines into clusters of grand staff systems, each one containing a staff corresponding to the right hand and another corresponding to the left hand. It is important to note that we are exclusively working with piano sheet music, where a grand staff consists of two staves connected by a brace and a line. At the end of this process, we obtain a prediction of the number of bar lines detected in the image.

The process used to obtain the bar lines of an image is showed in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: Bar Line detection process.

Then, with the midpoints of each staff detected in the image and the isolated bar lines, it is possible to determine the grouping of staves in the sheet music score. Each grand staff will correspond to a different cluster, where the pairs of detected staves will follow two different patterns: one grouping the staves 0-1, 2-3, 4-5, and another grouping them 1-2, 3-4, 5-6... Clustering them using this process ensures that incorrectly detected staves are not included in the final Bootleg Score representation. This step is extremely important for fixing possible errors made in previous sections. For example, the algorithm could incorrectly detect a staff line corresponding to the title of the musical piece during the previous step. However, after obtaining the bar line information, that staff will not be taken into account to generate the Bootleg Score.

```

#The first staff is equal to -1 because it will not be
    included in the final Bootleg Score
staveMapping = {0:-1, 1:0, 2:1, 3:2, 4:3, 5:4, 6:5, 7:6, 8:7}
nhclusters, clusterPairs = clusterNoteheads(staveIdxs,
    staveMapping)
#Each note is assigned to its corresponding cluster
nhclusters = [-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,-1,0,0,0,0,0,...]
#Indicate how the staff lines will be grouped
clusterPairs = [(0,1),(2,3),(4,5),(6,7)]

```

2.2.4 Bootleg Score generation

At this point, we have all the necessary information to generate the Bootleg Score representation. The first step is to generate a variable that includes a list with tuples. Each tuple has four elements: coordinates of each note in the image (it will be necessary to use a rescale factor to represent each note), their corresponding value saved in *nhvals*, and their corresponding cluster (*nhclusters*). An example of the resulting *nhdata* list is the following:

```

#First value: "Y" coordinate. Second value: "X" coordinate.
    Third value: "nhval". Fourth value: "nhCluster"
nhdata = [(70,672,-12,-1), (80,660,-15,-1)...]

```

Secondly, *generateImageBootlegScore()* iterates over the cluster pairs and calls *generateSingleBootlegLine()*. In the case of the first iteration, we will have the cluster pair (0,1), where staff 0 (clusterR=0) will correspond to the staff of the right hand, and staff 1 will correspond to the staff of the left hand (clusterL=1).

The code generates a line of music in Bootleg Score format from notehead data grouped into clusters corresponding to two specific staves. Tuples are sorted first along the x-axis and then along the y-axis. This way the notes are arranged according to their position in the musical score, from left to right and from top to bottom. For each single bootleg line, *collapseSimultaneousEvents()* groups the noteheads that are close to each other in the same column, assuming that these notes sound simul-

taneously. In other words, this function groups the simultaneous notes into events based on their proximity and returns a list of these events. An example of one event can be the following:

```
#First array: "Y" coordinates. Second array: "X" coordinates.
  Third array: "nhvals". Fourth array: "nhClusters"
collapsed[0] = ([336,320,334], [132,140,146], [-1,3,0],
  [0,0,0])
#In the first grand staff, there are 27 columns (grouping
  notes in the vertical axis).
len(collapsed) = 27
```

Now, the function *constructBootlegScore* encodes the previous information into the Bootleg Score representation. It is important to remind that this step is done inside the function *generateSingleBootlegLine()*, so in the first iteration, we will represent the notes corresponding to the cluster pair (0,1). As we explained in previous sections, the Bootleg representation is a matrix with dimensions of $62 \times N$, where 62 represents the possible staff positions and N represents the number of simultaneous events. The columns represent the notes of the piano, with the first 34 values (*rh_dim* = 34) corresponding to the notes from E3 to C8, and the other 28 values corresponding to the notes from A1 to G4, played with the left hand (*lh_dim* = 28).

For each event, the objective is to determine the placement of the noteheads in the matrix. The *getNoteheadPlacement()* function takes values and clusters as input and returns the vectors *rhvec* and *lhvec* indicating the location of the noteheads in the right and left hands, respectively. The note cluster is checked and the position of the notehead is adjusted in the corresponding vector (*rhvec* or *lhvec*). The adjustment is made by adding 11 to the position (position refers to the note value calculated previously and originally stored in the variable *nhval*) for the right hand (*cluster* = 0) and 17 for the left hand (*cluster* = 1). The function returns the values of the vectors *rhvec* and *lhvec* indicating the placement of the note heads in the arrays representing the right and left hands.

Next, in the *constructBootlegScore()* function, the matrices of the left and right

hand are vertically concatenated to obtain a matrix that represents both hands. Therefore, if we continue to take as an example the case in which the first pair of staves has 27 events in total, the dimension of the Bootleg Score representation would be a 62x27 matrix. The representation of each pair of clusters is concatenated on the horizontal axis. Having in account that in the *events* variable we have the most important information, such as the coordinates of the detected noteheads, it is possible to represent the original image together with the detected notes in order to look for possible errors that happens when obtaining the Bootleg Score representation.

The Bootleg Representation for each staff is concatenated along the horizontal axis. The final representation of the full page is represented as a single matrix with dimensions of 62xN. As mentioned in previous sections, when a PDF is opened, all pages are transformed into PNG files. Therefore, the process of obtaining the Bootleg Score concludes after concatenating all the representations obtained for each page. An example of the final representation for a sheet music fragment can be seen in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Bootleg Representation Example

2.3 IMSLP

The International Music Score Library Project (IMSLP) [16] is an online platform dedicated to provide access to a huge amount of classical music scores and related materials. such as music recordings. Founded in 2006, IMSLP has grown into one of the largest repositories of public domain and freely licensed sheet music, with compositions from famous composers and different genres and historical periods.

Through its different sections, users can explore, study, and perform classical music compositions, contributing to the preservation and appreciation of music. All of this is extremely useful for musicians, scholars, educators, and enthusiasts from all around the world. These characteristics make IMSLP [17] an excellent website to obtain the necessary PDF sheet music for this project. How the data was obtained will be explained in future sections.

2.4 Notable Works

In the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR), Pedro Ramoneda et al. work [18] presents an advancement in the state of the art in score difficulty classification. One of the problems they highlight is the lack of annotated datasets, and they address this by presenting a machine-readable piano score dataset with difficulty annotations. Additionally, for the machine learning tasks, they utilized MusicXML [19], another music representation that provides useful information for the necessary tasks. This work helps us understand the importance of having a good dataset [20], as previously mentioned, as well as the importance of choosing a music representation to achieve good performance in our main tasks.

Daniel Yang et al. [9] proposed a method to use the Bootleg Score representation to solve the problem in which an artist would like to know how a particular music fragment sounds taking a picture with his phone and listening to that particular fragment using its MIDI file. In this particular case, both MIDI and cell phone image are represented using the Bootleg Score representation and also using the subsequence DTW [21]. The results show an F-measure score of 0.869, indicating that using a low-dimensional feature representation such as the Bootleg Score can provide good results in the MIDI passage retrieval.

Additionally, some works use the Bootleg Score representation for other MIR tasks, such as predicting piano performance difficulty [22], instrument classification [23], composer style classification [11], piano sheet music retrieval [24] or MIDI sheet music alignment [25]. In conclusion, we can see that despite having a relatively new

representation, there is no doubt about its potential when it comes to extracting useful information for performing different tasks.

Chapter 3

Methodology

Once we understand how the Bootleg Representation works, it is possible to start working on the computational segmentation of PDF music books. In this section we will describe the methods used for data collection, GUI design, and analysis. It is important to remember the main objective of this project: to take advantage of the information available in *Piano Library* (small fragments of scores in PNG format), the information available in IMSLP (complete books) and the use of OMR to find the small fragments in those documents, finally obtaining a database with books segmented in different parts.

3.1 Piano Library

As mentioned in previous sections, to get the necessary data, we used the *Piano Library* website, which meets our requirements. It offers an extensive database of more than 5,000 piano musical pieces. This information includes useful statistics such as the difficulty of each piece, the composer, the duration, and a link to IMSLP for access to the complete score. Additionally, the website displays a small fragment in PNG format of all the pieces that make up the music score. Therefore, it is possible to compile data that will be very helpful for our task. Firstly, we have short fragments corresponding to individual compositions that belong to a complete music book. Secondly, we have a link to IMSLP, allowing us to access the complete

PDF. Finally, we have statistics on composers, duration, and more, which will be very useful for organizing the corresponding metadata of our dataset.

After scraping the website, a JSON file was generated that contained all the necessary metadata. At the same time, images in PNG format corresponding to the relevant fragments were stored. An example of a fragment stored in the JSON file is shown below.

```
"02842": {
    "composer_name": "scarlatti",
    "difficulty": 2.0,
    "duration": "3' 30\"",
    "idx_book": 0,
    "imslp_url": "https://imslp.org/wiki/
        Keyboard_Sonata_in_A_minor%2C_K.148_(Scarlatti%2
        C_Domenico)",
    "movement": "01",
    "mp3_path": "https://www.pianolibrary.org/composers/
        scarlatti/sonata-148/01.mp3",
    "png_path": "https://www.pianolibrary.org/composers/
        scarlatti/sonata-148/01.png",
    "work_name": "Sonata in A minor, K. 148",
    "work_url": "https://www.pianolibrary.org/composers/
        scarlatti/sonata-148"
}
```

By having several fragments that correspond to the same music book, the *idx_book* variable allows us to determine to which book each fragment belongs, thereby avoiding errors. Finally, **Table 1** shows the information related to the number of fragments and the number of PDF files containing each quantity.

Number of Fragments	Total PDF's with that Amount
1	1071
2	113
3	138
4	88
5	21
6	35
7	8
10	8
11	3
12	26
16	4
17	1
18	4
20	6
24	6
34	1
53	1
62	1

Table 1: Relation between number of fragments and total PDFs with that amount

3.2 Testing Bootleg Score

Regarding Bootleg Score, the first step involved carrying out a series of tests to check the viability of creating a dataset using the representation mentioned before as the main tool.

To do this, we used a couple of test PDFs as well as the PNGs of the corresponding fragments available on the *Piano Library* website. The objectives of this test were the following:

- First, to check if an adequate Bootleg representation of the PDF document

was obtained.

- Second, to perform the same process with the fragment corresponding to the individual composition.
- Finally, to find a way for the DTW algorithm to help us identify on the original music book the area of the PDF where the detection had been made.

DTW allows us to see how well two sequences match, even if they aren't perfectly synchronized. The main idea to check if the detection made using the DTW algorithm was correct was to display both the PDF page and the fragment in question. A red rectangle would indicate the area in which the fragment was located, or at least a part of it, to validate the detection.

As mentioned in the state of the art, the original Bootleg Score code provides an array of zeros and ones that represents information related to the noteheads and their position in the score. The first problem we encountered is that, with just this data, we cannot represent the exact position where the fragment has been detected on the screen.

Fortunately, during the process of obtaining the Bootleg representation, we can save a lot of additional information that is useful for understanding the analysis of a score. This information includes:

1. The coordinates in the image of each of the detected notes that will allow us to represent the rectangle that encompasses the detection in the final interface.
2. The number of notes in each Bootleg event.
3. The number of pages in the PDF document.
4. The scale factor applied to the image during the process of obtaining the Bootleg Score, ensuring that we can recover the original image accurately and avoid errors when representing the notes using the obtained coordinates.

5. The number of events for each of the pages, which will allow us to know when each page begins within the Bootleg representation.

Once all the necessary information had been collected, it was possible to create the code that implemented the DTW algorithm and displayed the page on which the detection was done correctly on the screen. To do this, once the Bootleg representation had been obtained, the reverse process had to be performed to return to the original score.

The DTW algorithm is responsible for finding the most probable position of an array (in this case, the Bootleg representation of the fragment) within a larger array (in our case, the Bootleg Score of the complete PDF), resulting in the position where the fragment starts within the Bootleg representation. This is why we needed to store the additional information mentioned in the previous paragraphs. Since we know the number of events on each of the PDF pages, it is possible to determine the PDF page on which the detection has been performed. Similarly, once we know the position of the array where the fragment begins, and since we also know its size, it is easy to determine where it ends. Additionally, in another variable, we have the coordinates of each note that appears in the Bootleg Score, as well as the scale factor to make them coincide with the original size of the image. With all the necessary data available, we can finally extract the coordinates of the first and last notes that have been detected. With a simple Python function, a rectangle will be drawn on the image with the upper-left corner at the first coordinate and the lower-right corner at the last coordinate. This process is shown in **Figure 6**.

Using Tkinter [26] to create the interface, it is possible to first select a PDF with the complete score, then choose the fragment we want to find, and finally display the result on the screen. To do this, it will be necessary to compute the Bootleg representation of both documents, which, depending on the case, could take a significant amount of time. The solution to this problem will be shown in future sections of the document. Next, as explained in previous paragraphs, we have all the necessary information to show the result. Therefore, if the detection is positive, a new tab

Figure 6: DTW Process to detect a fragment

will open, displaying both the PDF page with a rectangle indicating the area where the fragment has been detected and the fragment itself. It is important to show the fragment so that the user can quickly check if the detection corresponds to the fragment, as it is possible that, although the DTW algorithm returns a result, it may not be what we were looking for. Finally, two *YES* and *NO* buttons were added to allow the user to indicate if the detection was correct while allowing the program to continue opening other PDFs. An example of how this test interface works is shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7: Test Interface with detected fragment

After carrying out various tests with other music scores, it was found that the use of Bootleg Score to create a dataset of segmented PDFs could be possible. The next step will be to find an adequate number of documents with which to create that dataset.

3.3 PDF Music Books

In the previous sections, we emphasized the importance of IMSLP as a free repository containing thousands of classical music books. Furthermore, the huge amount of data available online presents a significant opportunity for conducting machine learning tasks that require this type of data and information. These tasks includes training and testing various approaches related to OMR and MIR.

3.3.1 Scraping IMSLP

In order to obtain data to use in our segmentation interface, it seems obvious that downloading the music books from IMSLP is the best option thanks to the links available in the JSON file obtained in the *Piano Library* section. The JSON file contains 1572 links to different IMSLP piano sheet music books. It also includes an ID value to differentiate the different files when downloading them. It is very important to understand that the links available on *Piano Library* reference the main page of the piece on IMSLP. Retrieving the PDF is very challenging because there are many options and steps before reaching the final document. With so many options available, it can be very tedious to select one by one which one might be more suitable or which one is of higher quality. That is why it was decided to perform an automatic process of downloading documents, in which all available files were downloaded, and finally filtered using the metadata available in IMSLP to keep the most useful versions for our task.

After taking a look at how IMSLP works, it is possible to see different problems when trying to download a huge amount of data from the website. First of all, when trying to download sheet music, the user has to accept a disclaimer about copyright and the way IMSLP works with sheet music. Secondly, the free version of IMSLP

makes the user wait at least 15 seconds to obtain the download link. Then, after all these steps and navigation through different windows, the user is finally able of downloading the PDF in a location of their choice. In our case, we want to have different versions of the same piece for the occasions in which the detection using the Bootleg Score do not work with one of the pieces. That means that if we want to download the PDF music books manually, it will take an incredibly high amount of time to achieve that, being tedious and time consuming. After thinking different options, we decided to use Selenium Python to download all the files in an automatic way.

3.3.2 Selenium Python

As S. Nyamathulla et al. mention in their article [27], Selenium is an open-source automated test suite that helps the automated testing of web applications. In our scenario, our objective is to perform web scraping by using this technology. Once the website is analyzed and the code is configured, it is possible to leave the computer on to download all the files. Mozilla Firefox was used during this task.

When conducting web scraping with Selenium, it's important to understand that we're simulating human clicks in the appropriate areas of the website to perform specific tasks. To identify these areas, we used the HTML code of IMSLP. The first issue we found was the *Accept cookies* button, which appears every time a new link is opened. Another important aspect to take into account is the appearance of the ChatBot [28], which is an intelligent machine-to-human conversation system and does not always appear, so catching its presence in specific cases is necessary. Therefore, it's important to close it before attempting to download a specific file. Managing these aspects is crucial because Selenium will not be able to obtain the sheet music data from the HTML if another aspect of the website, such as cookies or the ChatBot, is overlapping the main page.

Once we have finished preprocessing the web page, it is possible to start selecting which files can be downloaded. Depending on the score, different versions may be available. As explained before, it is important to have different versions of the same

sheet music for the situations in which fragment detection does not work correctly. Additionally, in most cases, the score will have *"Complete Score"* in the title, as we can see in **Figure 8**, making it the best indicator of possible sheet music to download.

Figure 8: IMSLP Example

Once we are on the main page, what we do is save all the locations in which the words *"Complete Score"* appear and then click on each of them. At the same time, we save all the possible metadata. As we can see in **Figure 8**, there are two options when obtaining the metadata. The first option is that there is only available information about the file size, number of pages, rating and total downloads. The other option includes, in addition to the previous one, a table containing information about the Editor, Publisher, Copyright, and more. An example of the code to obtain all the *'Complete Score'* sheet music books is the following:

```
score_buttons = driver.find_elements(By.XPATH, "//span[
    contains(text(), 'Complete Score')"])
```

All the metadata is saved in a JSON file. Then, after clicking in one of the *"Complete Score"* buttons, there are different options before obtaining the final PDF that we are going to download:

1. It is necessary to accept a disclaimer, wait 15 seconds, and then click to obtain the PDF.
2. A different window appears in which you also have to accept a disclaimer to obtain the PDF download link.

3. The PDF is directly available when clicking on the "Complete Score" button (less common option).

At the end of the process in which we deal with different windows before reaching the PDF sheet music book, the element that we need to find is the link that contain the PDF. In terms of HTML, we extract the *href* attribute. When downloading the different versions of a sheet music, the we used the ID provided in the JSON file with all the IMSLP links. This ID matches the one specified in the JSON that contains the fragments information, so it is possible to know which fragments belong to each music score. For example, if one book has the ID 154, the different versions will be save as 154_0, 154_1. 154_2...

After checking the script's performance and fixing different errors and bugs that appeared during the process, it was time to let the computer do the work automatically. After approximately 10 days of uninterrupted running, the script scraped all the links in the JSON file and downloaded the necessary music books. The final results of the web scraping are shown in **Table 2**.

Number of composers	38
Number of files	6137
Total size downloaded	27 GB

Table 2: Final results of IMSLP Scraping

Taking into account the performance of the web scraping script, its useful applications for working with sheet music books, and the room for improvement in the programming aspect, all the code is open source with the idea of continuing to improve the automation of file downloading.

3.4 Final Interface

After obtaining the necessary files to create the dataset, these being the complete music score as well as different fragments that belong to it, it was possible to begin

designing the interface that will allow the user to indicate and save the different information required to locate each fragment within each music score.

To achieve this, we used the interface generated for the test in section 3.2 as a starting point. We encountered another problem: for the annotation to be efficient, the detection results need to be displayed on the screen as quickly as possible. As mentioned in previous sections, the main issue with obtaining the Bootleg representation of a PDF with numerous pages is that it can take too long. Therefore, we decided to store all the necessary information from both the PDFs and the PNG fragments in Pickle files [29]. This way, the only action required is to open the corresponding Pickle file and perform the necessary checks from there.

When obtaining the Pickle files for each PDF, we decided to discard sheet music books with more than 35 pages because the machine used during this project could not handle the computational cost of obtaining the complete Bootleg representation. Additionally, considering that the number of versions available for the same music score could exceed 20 in some cases, the *'number of downloads'* attribute was used to retain a maximum of three versions for each document. As a result of these adjustments, the number of available PDFs was reduced to approximately 1500.

At this point, all the data necessary was available to create an interface that would allow the most optimal annotation possible. One folder contained the Pickle files for the PDFs downloaded from IMSLP and a JSON file with the corresponding metadata. Another folder contained all the fragments in PDF format (converted after scraping the *Piano Library*, since the fragments are displayed on the page in PNG format) along with a JSON file containing information for each fragment.

To make the entire process of opening fragments and complete scores as efficient as possible, the following steps were followed:

1. First, a fragment is opened, and its corresponding ID is obtained.
2. Second, the DTW algorithm is applied to all PDFs that have the same ID. This means that if there are three versions of the same work, the same fragment

will be detected in each of them.

3. If the detection is successful, the user presses the *YES* button, and a new window appears allowing them to select the area of the page in which the fragment is located.
4. Finally, all the information is stored in a JSON file.

An aspect that was added and had not been shown until now is mentioned in point 3 of the previous list. If the fragment has been correctly detected, it is necessary to indicate the exact area where it begins to avoid errors. Therefore, a final tab was designed in which the user selects the exact location in which the fragment begins, using a horizontal red line for precise adjustment, along with the ability to zoom in and out for better accuracy. In our case, the most important data was the *Y* coordinate of the page, which indicates the position of a new individual composition. After selecting the exact point where the piece is located, the user presses the *Save Detection Data* button and the interface will show another fragment/PDF to continue annotating.

Figure 9: Fragment Detection on the Final Interface

Figure 10: Final Annotation on the Final Interface

3.5 Dataset Creation

Regarding the creation of the dataset, it is necessary to take into account what type of information you want to know about each music score. In our case, the parameters of interest are: the name of the PDF file that contains the complete score (*PDF File*), the name of the file that belongs to the fragment (*Fragment File*), the *Y* coordinate where the detection was carried out (*PDF Page*), the dimensions of the image to enable rescaling if necessary and to avoid discrepancies with the *Y* coordinate value (*Image Width* and *Image Height*), and finally, the number of pages in the complete score, which will allow us to analyze the results in more depth, as we will see in future sections. An example of how successful detection data is collected is shown below.

```
"0_3_fragment_02842": {
  "PDF File": "0_3.pdf",
  "Fragment File": "02842.pdf",
```

```
"Y coordinate": 575.0,  
"PDF Page": "1",  
"Image Width": 2550,  
"Image Height": 3300,  
"PDF Total Pages": "2"  
}
```

Finally, after verifying the correct operation of both the interface and the information storage, it was time to start the annotation process. This process lasted around three weeks, during which we observed and selected cases where the use of the DTW algorithm and the Bootleg Score representation successfully allowed a music book to be correctly segmented.

Chapter 4

Results

In this section, an analysis of the final results will be shown. Various factors will be taken into account, such as the number of compositions per composer, the distribution of their difficulty, how the dataset is divided, the useful information obtained and the importance of having a dataset with segmented music books.

4.1 Automatic Annotation

First of all, we can show the accuracy of the automatic detection part. As we can see in **Figure 11**, the Bootleg detection was not always successful, with most of the books having at least one fragment that was not annotated. For example, the mean detection accuracy for sheet music books with four available fragments was approximately 70 %, meaning that usually one of the four fragments was not detected.

4.2 Manual Annotation

The music books have to be completely annotated in order to have a well-made dataset. Considering that the Automatic Annotation accuracy was approximately 70%, Manual Annotation was needed to correctly annotate all the individual compositions. This is because, in order to avoid noise in a machine learning environment,

Figure 11: Mean Detection Accuracy

it is necessary to have the PDFs with all the pieces detected. In order to achieve that, all the files were manually checked and completed by hand. After two weeks of work, the final results are showed in **Table 3**. An example of the JSON file containing all the metadata is shown at **Figure 12**. As we can see, all the information is saved, including the composer, the difficulty, the page, and the exact location of the piece.

Total Of PDFs	1597
Individual Compositions	2925

Table 3: Final Results after Manual Annotation

4.3 Train and Test Set

PDFs are separated into two groups, depending on the number of pieces in the document. On one side, we have the books with only one piece, and on the other side, the books with more than one piece. The number of documents for each set can be seen in **Table 4**.

Having only one composition means that we know the start and end of the piece in the document. This set can be used in a deep learning model for the Training Set,

```

{
  "0_3_fragment_02842": {
    "PDF File": "0_3.pdf",
    "Fragment File": "02842.pdf",
    "Y coordinate": 575.0,
    "PDF Page": "1",
    "Image Width": 2550,
    "Image Height": 3300,
    "PDF Total Pages": "2",
    "composer_name": "scarlatti",
    "difficulty": 2.0
  },
  "0_2_fragment_02842": {
    "PDF File": "0_2.pdf",
    "Fragment File": "02842.pdf",
    "Y coordinate": 410.0,
    "PDF Page": "1",
    "Image Width": 2550,
    "Image Height": 3606,
    "PDF Total Pages": "2",
    "composer_name": "scarlatti",
    "difficulty": 2.0
  }
},

```

Figure 12: JSON file example

Train Set	1221
Test Set	376

Table 4: Train and Test Split

generating synthetic books automatically via Data Augmentation [30], and the set with all the pieces segmented can be used for the Test Set.

It is important to note that both sets contain some documents with cover or index pages. So another contribution was to identify the location of the first composition in order to ignore those pages that do not contain useful information for Music Information Retrieval tasks.

4.4 Dataset Statistics

In this case, information is shown for both sets, where the user can access to a document in which all the statistics for both sets is included, and all the information related to the number of documents, composers or difficulties can be obtained. Some

examples are shown in **Figures 13, 14, 15 and 16.**

Figure 13: Number Of Pieces For Each Difficulty (Train Set)

Figure 14: Number Of Pieces For Each Difficulty (Test Set)

Figure 15: Number Of Pieces For Each Document (Test Set)

Figure 16: Number Of Documents For Each Composer (Test Set)

4.5 Importance of segmentation

It is important to show the relevance of having all the pieces correctly annotated. Having a new piece in the middle of the book does not necessarily mean that it starts at the beginning of the page. For example, in **Figure 17** we have two different cases.

1. On the left side, we have a case in which there is more than one piece.
2. On the right side, we have a case in which there is only one new composition in the page, but it is not located at the beginning of it.

The figure consists of two side-by-side images of musical score pages. The left image shows a page with four systems of music, each system separated by a red horizontal line. The right image shows a page with four systems of music, with a red horizontal line placed under the second system, indicating a new piece starting in the middle of the page.

Figure 17: Segmentation Examples

Having this examples, it is possible to confirm that another contribution of this dataset is to take these cases into account and correctly annotate them in order to avoid mistakes in future tasks.

4.6 Final Dataset

Finally, both the final dataset and the detailed information about the statistics can be found at the following link ([Segmented Music Books Dataset](#)). If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact the author of this project.

Chapter 5

Discussion

The main challenge addressed in this thesis was to create a dataset of segmented music books in a way that does not require much manual effort from the user. It is known that trying to obtain this type of data can be extremely tedious and time consuming. This work becomes more important when, after trying to find similar data on the internet, there is a lack of information available.

During this project, I introduced a new methodology to create a dataset semi automatically. While doing this, I also understood the importance and difficulty of obtaining datasets in the fields of Music Information Retrieval and Optical Music Recognition.

The lack of data can be linked to the IMSLP script part, where a code was also developed to automatically download sheet music books. It is important to highlight that one of the main problems with segmenting music books into individual compositions is not only the tediousness or time-consuming nature of the task, but the difficulty of obtaining the books themselves. Using Selenium Python to automatically download books from IMSLP demonstrated that there are immense music libraries on the internet and that the only necessary improvement is how we work with them.

Before starting this project, we already knew the complexity of the task and the

potential of Bootleg Score in searching for a short fragment within a music book. Despite the results shown in the previous section, the use of Bootleg Score was essential for dataset creation and time saving. If we talk about the limitations of this project, one of them is the amount of data included in the dataset, which can be incremented if we obtained more samples. This can be expanded in future work and improved to achieve faster segmentation.

5.1 Bootleg Score Tutorial

As a researcher, having the opportunity to discover a new music representation that allows to do a lot of tasks and that does not require much computational power was a mind blowing experience related to the range of possibilities that the OMR and MIR field offer when working with sheet music. That is the reason of publishing a simple tutorial to promote the Bootleg Score. This tutorial was published in the *HackerNoon* website, which is a technology-focused news website with 4 million monthly readers. It can be found in this link (How to Use Bootleg Score: A Low Resource Optical Music Recognition System)

There is a prominent future for this representation within the OMR community, and it is necessary to facilitate the first approach for new researchers in order to understand how it really works.

5.2 Future Work

Finally, the most important contribution was the dataset itself with the segmented books. It is the first step toward further retrieval and search in large music library collections. There is a huge amount of useful information on the internet, and now we have to use it.

For future work, this project represents an advance in many different real world tasks related to MIR, OMR and exploration of large collections of music and digital libraries. For example, composer classification, structure classification, technique classification, difficulty classification, retrieval or recommendation.

5.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, this project has opened numerous doors for future tasks that need music books divided into individual compositions, as well as including all the metadata for each one, allowing users to have all the information available at any moment. In my opinion, doing this thesis has been an amazing experience in which I have learned a lot of things, understanding the importance and difficulties that the field of MIR has nowadays, but also seeing the vast possibilities for the future that we have.

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